

Impact of seaway development on social development

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Abstract

In the article, it is analyzed that the process of discovery of the main intercontinental sea routes began in the 15th century, that the opening of new sea routes has its own necessary and objective reasons, and that the discovery of the sea route to the east caused a sharp change in the social and economic situation of the world.

Key words: sea, road, communication, trade, economy, development.

INTRODUCTION

The process of discovery of the main intercontinental sea routes began in the 15th century. The opening of new sea routes had its necessary and objective reasons. The main reason for this was that, by this time, European trade relations with Asian countries had been greatly reduced. Silk, silk and other types of fabrics, spices such as pepper, ginger, and other necessary products, imported from the East, which are very necessary for Europeans, almost did not arrive¹. It is known

¹ Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов, Абдулазиз Вахоб Ўғли Воитжонов, Жавоҳир Хожиакбар Ўғли

that these products were brought to Europe via the land "Great Silk Road". The main point of this road leading from Asia to Europe was the city of Constantinople. This city was conquered by the Ottoman Turks in 1453 and renamed Istanbul.

MAIN PART

But the work did not end only with the renaming of the city. Because the relations of the European countries with the Ottoman Turks, who were expanding their territory to the west, were not good. Between them, mutual disputes escalated and military wars took place. Due to constant enmity, the Turks completely blocked the trade routes from east to west. At first, the land route was closed. Then, the Turkish state's powerful naval forces closed the sea routes through the Mediterranean Sea and the Black Sea. So, the ancient trade routes that connected Europe with the East for thousands of years ended. This situation did not go unnoticed. It began to have a negative impact on the social and economic development of European countries. Especially, this negative effect began to be seen very noticeably in the everyday life of the population. The search for new sea routes connecting Europe with the East became a matter of life and death. Therefore, the governments of most countries in Europe are trying to open a sea route from the East to the West, and they are encouraging the activities of sailors and travelers who want to conduct research in this regard. The most active in this matter were the governments of Portugal and Spain.

One of the first countries to show interest in opening new sea routes to the East was Portugal. Portuguese sailors believed that it was possible to go to the

countries of the East by going around the African continent and began to implement their plans step by step². They moved south from the west coast of Africa. And on this basis, they mastered and studied their ways. But this process was very slow. The Portuguese arrived in Calcutta, India in May 1498. It was a huge discovery for its time. The discovery of a sea route with the East, which is the eternal dream of Europeans, caused a sharp change in the social and economic situation of the world. The discovery of intercontinental sea routes dramatically changed world trade relations³. Some cities and ports in the Mediterranean, which were once trade centers, have lost their importance. New trade centers and ports were formed in their place. Because world trade relations have moved from the Mediterranean Sea to the oceans of the world.

The fact that the Portuguese went around Africa and found their way to India accelerated the movement of other European countries, especially Spain. After that, many previously unknown lands were discovered, new sea routes were laid across the seas and oceans of the world. Development also entered the discovered territories. The volume of trade relations of Europe with other continents began to increase. It was an important factor in the development of science and technology and the creation of industry⁴. The opening of sea routes and the development of

² Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов, Абдулазиз Вахоб Ўғли Воитжонов, Жавохир Хожиакбар Ўғли Маматқулов КИШИЛИК ЖАМИЯТИДА ДЕНГИЗ ТРАНСПОРТИНИНГ АҲАМИЯТИ БОРАСИДАГИ ДИАЛЕКТИК ЁНДОШУВЛАР // Академические исследования в области педагогических наук. 2022. №11.

³ Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов, Толмасбек Анвар Ўғли Шодмонов, Улуғбек Жеткербай Ўғли Уразбаев (2022). МАМЛАКАТНИНГ БАРҚАРОР ТАРАҚҚИЁТИНИ ТАЪМИНЛАБ БЕРИШДА ЙЎЛЛАРНИНГ ТУТГАН ЎРНИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (11), 309-314.

⁴ Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов, Толмасбек Анвар Ўғли Шодмонов, Улуғбек Жеткербай Ўғли Уразбаев (2022). МАМЛАКАТНИНГ БАРҚАРОР ТАРАҚҚИЁТИНИ ТАЪМИНЛАБ БЕРИШДА ЙЎЛЛАРНИНГ

maritime transport gave many countries the opportunity to establish direct relations. Because, in the early days when land routes were a priority, countries had to pass through the territories of other countries in their mutual relations. The political situation in some countries made the roads through these countries dangerous or completely closed. There is no such problem on sea routes. As long as there is access to the sea, countries can communicate with each other without any obstacles. Sea routes had the following advantages over land routes. These were time and cost issues. Time Matters - This means that the destination is reached faster by sea routes than by land routes⁵. Because the main means of transport on land at that time consisted of horses and camels, and because of the heavy loads, they moved very slowly. Places that took years to reach on land became accessible in months by sea. The question of cost - it is known that the movement of overland trade caravans was very expensive. Several hundred horses and camels were needed to transport goods. Fodder was always bought for these animals. Dozens of porters were needed to load and unload cargo in the caravan. Porters and other servants in the caravan were paid. A lot of money was required to feed, clothe and rest in caravansary for the people in the caravan, who would take part in arduous journeys lasting months and years. These expenses did not fail to affect the products transported in trade caravans. Costs were relatively lower in trade processes carried out by ships on sea routes. hundreds of horses and camels loaded onto one ship. The number of the ship's crew was also much less than the

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⁵ Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов, Абдулазиз Вахоб Ўғли Воитжонов, Жавоҳир Хожиакбар Ўғли Маматкулов КИШИЛИК ЖАМИЯТИДА ДЕНГИЗ ТРАНСПОРТИНИНГ АҲАМИЯТИ БОРАСИДАГИ ДИАЛЕКТИК ЁНДОШУВЛАР // Академические исследования в области педагогических наук. 2022. №11.

number of members of the convoy. Then the ships stopped as often as the caravans and did not rest in the caravansary and so on.

CONCLUSION

So sea routes were preferred over land caravan routes⁶. Countries with access to sea routes began to abandon the use of land caravan routes. As a result, the importance of land caravan routes gave way to sea routes. This situation lasted for several hundred years. When land-based automobiles and railroad-powered steam locomotives were invented to compete with seagoing ships, land routes began to regain their place and importance. After all, automobiles and railroads were far ahead of their predecessor caravan routes in terms of speed, efficiency, productivity, and features.

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⁶ Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов, Абдулазиз Вахоб Ўғли Воитжонов, Жавоҳир Хожиакбар Ўғли Маматқулов КИШИЛИК ЖАМИЯТИДА ДЕНГИЗ ТРАНСПОРТИНИНГ АҲАМИЯТИ БОРАСИДАГИ ДИАЛЕКТИК ЁНДОШУВЛАР // Академические исследования в области педагогических наук. 2022. №11.